

PROVIDING ACADEMIC MOBILITY OF STUDENTS ON THE BASE OF INDIVIDUAL EDUCATIONAL TRAJECTORY

Khimmataliev Dustnazar Omonovich

Doctor of pedagogical sciences, professor, Chirchik State Pedagogical University

<https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.8248373>

***Abstract.** Individual educational trajectory develops universality, variability, choice and other abilities of students. The article covers issues of improving the quality of students' education and the effectiveness of scientific research by providing academic mobility of students based on individual educational trajectory.*

***Keywords:** integration, education, component, principle, perspective, content, person.*

In teaching on the basis of an individual educational trajectory, the student is considered as an independent, self-directed person with certain social experiences that can be used by other students and teachers, with his own personal goals and projects, knowledge and educational needs. Therefore, the student determines and takes into account his individual abilities and opportunities mainly independently, however, he uses the experience of other students and the experience of the teacher. The teacher appears as a teacher, consultant, expert, organizer, source of various knowledge and high personal qualities in the educational process. At the age of a student, the processes of integration of the individual prevail in the society, therefore, developing his individuality, the student enriches the personality of other participants of the pedagogical process with his individual characteristics.

In the process of individual education, the individual's goals, development, and desire for perfection are realized, and relations with teachers and students are expanded, lessons are conducted individually. In teaching on the basis of an individual educational trajectory, the student is considered as an independent, self-directed person with certain social experiences that can be used by other students and teachers, with his own personal goals and projects, knowledge and educational needs. Therefore, the student determines and takes into account his individual abilities and opportunities mainly independently, however, he uses the experience of other students and the experience of the teacher. The teacher appears as a teacher, consultant, expert, organizer, source of various knowledge and high personal qualities in the educational process. At the age of a student, the processes of integration of the individual prevail in the society, therefore, developing his individuality, the student enriches the personality of other participants of the pedagogical process with his individual characteristics.

In the process of individual education, the individual's goals, development, and desire for perfection are realized, and relations with teachers and students are expanded, lessons are conducted individually.

Individual education includes the formation of educational content based on the principles of personal development of students and teachers, diversity of didactic homomorphisms, perspective, universality, variability, choice and context, which provides the possibility of teaching in the unity of the individual, subjective and metaobjective component of individual education, it corresponds to stages of personalized learning such as adaptation, labilization, integration, as well as macrophase. Among them are problem-searching, research and creative methods, design and programming activities based on the principles of fundamentalization and polysubjectivity.

In ensuring the academic mobility of students on the basis of the individual educational trajectory, individual-oriented educational technologies, methods of preparing students for self-education, self-education, and self-development occupy a special place. Academic mobility provides full-time, part-time, evening students and scientific-pedagogical staff of higher education institutions with education in cooperation with foreign educational institutions and scientific centers within the framework of partnership and cooperation.

The purpose of academic mobility:

- to increase the quality of education and the efficiency of scientific research;
- establishment of external and internal integration relations and use of world educational resources;
- implementation of joint educational and scientific-research programs on the priority directions of science development at the higher educational institution;
- ensuring the competitiveness of young scientific and pedagogical staff, graduate students and students in the domestic and international labor market;
- increasing the prestige of the higher education institution in the market of educational services;
- training of scientific-pedagogical personnel and other employees of the higher educational institution, etc.

The main organizational mechanisms of academic mobility of students are obtaining a foreign diploma and its application, testing system (credits) ECTS, as well as mobility and recognition information network centers.

On the basis of the individual educational trajectory, in ensuring academic mobility of students, identification, consideration and development of their individual abilities, improvement of their individual way of thinking and its globalization is ensured, high local level of knowledge is achieved. Providing academic mobility of students on the basis of an individual educational trajectory develops in students the ability to be an individual, the ability to personally continue oneself in another person in the future professional activity, enriches the path of communication and activity with people who are the object of relationships with their own personality, as well as in their life path.

Providing academic mobility of students based on an individual educational trajectory is based on the principles of andragogic and "local" growth. Treating the student as an adult creates the necessary conditions for not only horizontal, but also vertical individualization. To develop personal learning abilities, scientific-methodical work skills, to improve and improve their skills, analysis of their own activities is carried out by students with the task of developing educational tasks and tasks of various levels and carrying out personal research by them. Students do such work in the course of practical training on the use of ICT tools in the educational process, learning the theory and methodology of teaching. Educational discussions and conferences, brainstorming, role-playing and business games, educational modeling and design, and a combination of teaching and research also help their personal development. The use of educational technologies based on pair and group work, business games, trainings, etc. also helps the development of interpersonal relations.

REFERENCES

1. Беязкин А.М. Академическая мобильность и качество обучения за рубежом / А. М. Беязкин // Казанский педагогический журнал: Изд-во «Магариф», 2007. - №2. - С.115 – 122.
2. Галичин В.А. Академическая мобильность в условиях интернационализации образования / В.А. Галичин, Е.А.Карпухина, В.В.Матвеев, А.П.Сугакова. – М. : Университетская книга, 2009. – 460 с.